

Governance in the Blockchain

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Abstract

1. Introduction

Governance - what is it (good for)? - What is it again? - Why do we need it? Governance in the Blockchain - Is technology different than society? - Technology can run itself, can't? - What specific governance challenges arise Governance - what is it not? - Governance \neq Compliance, \neq accounting, \neq a once a year thing - Governance is how you - as you and your company - want to be seen and perceived by others. Governance - what is important to know - Governance works for you - Is work in progress. Governance - what to do about it - Remember the blockchain principles. - Match governance to the kind of company you want to be.

2. Material and methods

When reviewing your conferences highlights, I feel an affinity/strong understanding (from a non-technological point of view) with: - The Future of Blockchain and Humanity - Blockchain and trust managements - Blockchain Technology - Blockchain in crowdsensing - Blockchain schemes for decentralization - Privacy and trust of blockchain and decentralized schemes - Theories of blockchain and its evolution Please find attached my bio, which gives a good overview of my activities and credentials to date. "Governance in the Blockchain".

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